
СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

УДК 304.4

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14017391

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Казахстанская практика сохранение и защита культурного наследия (социально-политический анализ)

Аннотация. Авторы рассматривают ключевые направления социально-политической институционализации историко-культурного наследия казахского народа, анализируют факторы и условия интеграции духовного потенциала историко-культурных ценностей в государственно-политическое развитие современного Казахстана. Статья позволяет определить уровень и эффективность институциональных основ сохранения историко-культурного наследия, их дифференциацию в региональном и отраслевом аспектах. Практическая значимость сформулированных в статье выводов и предложений заключается в определении приоритетов перехода к новой модели социально-культурной политики нового Казахстана. Эмпирическую основу статьи составляют междисциплинарные исследования отечественных и зарубежных учёных по сохранению культурного наследия и охране культурно-исторических памятников, стратегические документы по повышению культурного потенциала Республики Казахстан.

Ключевые слова: культурного наследие, государственно-политические факторы, региональная политика, культурные ценности, модернизации социально-политических основ, культурная политика.

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Kazakhstan's practice of preserving and protecting cultural heritage (socio-political analysis)

Abstract. The relevance of the article lies in the fact that the authors consider the main directions of socio-political institutionalization of the historical and cultural heritage of the Kazakh people, analyze the factors and conditions of integration of the spiritual potential of historical and cultural values into the state and political development of modern Kazakhstan. The article allows to determine the level and effectiveness of institutional frameworks for preservation of historical and cultural heritage, their differentiation in regional and sectoral aspects. The practical significance of the conclusions and proposals formed in the article lies in the determination of the priorities of the transition to a new model of socio-cultural policy of the new Kazakhstan. The empirical basis of the article is formed by interdisciplinary studies of domestic and foreign scientists on preservation of cultural heritage and protection of cultural and historical monuments, strategic documents on improvement of cultural potential of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Key words: cultural heritage, state-political factors, regional policy, cultural values, modernization of socio-political foundations, cultural policy.

Modern trends of socio-economic and socio-political development, transformation of the state and political arrangement objectively assume and "rely" on the actualization of the accumulated civilizational potential, historical experience, effectiveness of ethno-social spatial structures. It is in this context that the solution to one of the most important socio-political problems of deepening national and civic identity in Kazakh society is seen.

In this regard, the Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor E.B. Sydykov, reasonably notes that "even from this point of view, it can be positioned as bringing into the "historical order" the true view of the steppe civilizations, the creative past of the most ancient peoples of the Eurasian continent" [1].

Over the past thirty years, the "passive" understanding of the role of heritage conservation, the diversification of the mechanisms of its institutionalization and the formation of a specific list of objects of material and spiritual content have been overcome in the social sciences and cultural policy in general. To move from the formula "history teaches" to the formula "history shows", and in fact to demonstrate a positive view of the historical panorama of events of universal significance" [2, p. 151], - this is the creative goal of the system of revival and preservation of historical and cultural values and historical and cultural heritage in our country. The implementation of the above-mentioned scientific and practical problem depends on the segmentation of such concepts as "historical and cultural values" and "historical

and cultural heritage" in republican and regional development programmes, on modernizing and reinterpreting the instruments and rules for preserving and supporting them. The President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, K.K. Tokayev, has rightly set the following strategic task: 'For the modernization of the country, we must effectively use the soft power of our national brand, history and culture. This approach will help to strengthen the positive image of the country. We have inherited a huge heritage from our ancestors. It needs to be consistently modernized and promoted around the world. For example, the Mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed Yassawi is considered one of the symbols of our unique history and occupies a special place in the system of our spiritual values' [3].

The purpose of this problem is connected with the need for a new "reading" of many thousands of years of historical experience and heritage of the Kazakh people, formation of a modern case of socio-cultural values, achievement of parameters of high civic identity, active participation in the international global and mega-regional integration community, modernisation of historical consciousness of the Kazakh society. Therefore, it is of fundamental importance and expedient to strengthen the national ideology of preservation of the historical and cultural heritage of the people of Kazakhstan, which unites all strata and generations of the population of the country.

In the context of the concept of the New Kazakhstan, this ideology should be given a

clearer and more socially visible outline and parameters for the assessment and measurement of its effectiveness.

In our view, the move towards an effective model of protection and preservation of the country's historical and cultural heritage should be linked to overcoming a number of systemic problems in this area of cultural policy:

- Imbalance of the mechanisms of regulation of cultural heritage at the international and national levels.

- Lack of adequate main and supplementary sources of financing for the protection, restoration and preservation of cultural, architectural and historical monuments.

- Imperfection of the republican normative-legal basis of state regulation of the preservation of historical and cultural heritage.

- The absence of a stable and independent structure of state heritage management at both the republican and regional levels.

- The lack of development of criteria for the inclusion of certain objects in the list of historical and cultural heritage monuments.

- The imbalance in classifying more objects of material culture as historical and cultural heritage monuments than spiritual values of national importance.

- Insufficient integration of the historical and cultural heritage into the educational, informational, scientific and cognitive development spheres.

- lack of modern medium-term sectoral, regional and national programmes for the preservation of the country's historical and cultural heritage.

The definition of a set of socio-political priorities for the provision and implementation of a new approach to the preservation of the historical and cultural heritage of the Kazakhstani society is required.

It should be mentioned here that, in addition to the general principles of modernization of the system of preservation of historical and cultural heritage, it is important

to consider the specific ethnographic and historical features of its formation in Kazakhstan.

Among the basic socio-political priorities, first of all, the system-forming role of the legislative support of the processes of preservation of the historical and cultural heritage in Kazakhstan should be highlighted.

Currently, the national legislative support for regulating the historical and cultural heritage in the country is determined by the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Culture" and the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Protecting and Using Historical and Cultural Heritage Monuments". The practical experience shows that the main purpose of these legal acts is to institutionalize the main concepts and notions forming the system of "historical and cultural values - historical and cultural heritage".

However, almost the entire complex of regulating mechanisms for this process is in the "subordinate" regulatory framework (Government resolutions, orders of Ministries and committees of the country) of the executive authorities.

This state of affairs does not solve the problem of so-called interdepartmental disagreement and short-termism of their decisions.

Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the preservation of historical and cultural heritage as a component of the protection of the national interests of the country should be strengthened and ensured by relevant articles at the legislative level of the country.

What are the aspects of the preservation of the historical and cultural heritage of the country that should be reflected in the relevant national legislation in the form of independent sections or articles?

We believe that it should be accompanied by defining the legal status of historical and cultural heritage objects and by a detailed list of their types and forms. Moreover, the existing division of cultural and historical heritage objects between the Republic and the regions not only leads to a "dis-

sonance" in the objectivity and clarity of the criteria for the classification of cultural and historical monuments, but also reduces the social and political potential of the very idea of distinguishing the historical and cultural heritage as an element of state formation.

Therefore, it would be appropriate to consider a transition to the Unified List of Heritage Monuments. The preservation of monuments requires the organization of appropriate monitoring of their condition and expert assessment of necessary restoration measures. That is, these mechanisms of monument protection and procedures for their implementation should be established at the level of the country's laws. The problem of state control over privately owned cultural heritage sites located on purchased lands and territorial plots also requires a balanced approach. The relevant laws of the country should describe in detail the right of the state to exercise control over these objects and, if necessary, to alienate them into state ownership.

The next socio-political priority is to integrate the national system of protection of historical and cultural heritage into an identical international normative-legal space.

It is impossible not to agree with A.S. Bulatova, who states that "monuments of the past concentrate valuable knowledge about traditions and life patterns of many generations of people, and therefore the world community has a responsibility to preserve these sources of information so that they can be passed on to future generations". The preservation of globally significant cultural heritage on the territory of a single country should be of direct interest to the entire world community, since the implementation of the concept of sustainable development consists in particular in creating conditions for the transmission of cultural heritage to future generations. Therefore, in order to eliminate the hotbeds of military and political conflicts in areas of special historical and cultural significance, coordinated action by the UN system of organizations and leading countries is required" [4].

Naturally, the UNESCO Conventions for the Protection of the World Cultural and

Natural Heritage and for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage have been the 'driving force' in the formation of international rules. For Kazakhstan, the participation in the UNESCO programmes has been marked by the inclusion of a number of objects of the tangible and natural heritage in the World Heritage List. This important part of the cultural policy of the country has a high potential for the recognition of the values of the Great Steppes at the international level.

In this context, more active steps should be taken, in particular in the following directions:

- Overcoming the imbalance in support measures between tangible and intangible heritage;

This approach is very important for Kazakhstan, as the majority of the cultural heritage is most clearly expressed in its intangible forms:

- Inclusion of historical and cultural heritage objects and values that are currently outside the territory of Kazakhstan in the process of preservation. There are already positive experiences in this direction, in particular in the restoration of the Al-Farabi Mausoleum, the Beibarys Mosque and others.

- To recognise and take an active part in the processes of the securitisation of cultural heritage objects.

This legal form is gradually becoming an effective norm for the protection of the cultural heritage from the illegal confiscation and repression.

This process requires recognizing and participating in implementing the main provisions of the UNIDROIT Convention on Stolen or Illegally Exported Cultural Property.

In the modern conditions, the effectiveness of the measures for the protection of historical and cultural monuments is also directly related to the financial and economic basis of their implementation.

The priority of this direction is predetermined by the high degree of economiza-

tion of this area of cultural policy. In fact, the level of the corresponding economic "cushion" for its provision is directly proportional to the timeliness and scope of measures to protect the cultural heritage.

In this case, there is an active process of transformation of the potential of historical and cultural heritage into a genuine incentive for the development of other economic sectors. This provision was formed as a strategically significant at the level of the "Concept of cultural policy in the Republic of Kazakhstan" [5].

We would like to draw your attention to a rather comprehensive and meaningful scientific opinion of the Doctor of Philosophy, Professor J.J. Moldabekov: "The cultural heritage, as a part and a continuation of the culture, acquires its ideological and moral autonomy. Cultural heritage, as a part and continuation of culture, acquires its ideological and moral autonomy, referring firstly to the living spiritual creativity of generations of like-minded individuals, and secondly to the sphere of material production, technology, industry and time infrastructure" [6].

The following organizational tasks should be taken care of by the authorities of the State:

- To make changes in the direction of liberalization of inter-budgetary relations in the field of protection and maintenance of cultural heritage objects.

- Provide for the application of tax incentives for organizations and companies that restore historical and cultural monuments and invest in the creation of logistical infrastructure around heritage sites.

- Update ethno-tourism development projects within the framework of the national strategy for the development of the tourism industry in Kazakhstan.

- Generally, promote the diversification of financial sources of support for the country's cultural heritage sites.

A special place among the socio-political priorities is occupied by the leveling of the regional levels of the state of historical and cultural heritage.

It is not a question of deepening the 'regionalization' of heritage significance, but rather of creating an equal and mutually presupposing historical and cultural environment in all regions of the country. The unification of regional differences and the transition to a single model of protection and allocation of historical and cultural monuments corresponds to the national security interests of a sovereign state. This requires equal representation of all areas (regions and cities of Astana, Almaty, Shymkent) in the National List of Historical and Cultural Heritage Objects.

At the same time, the implementation of the general task should be ensured by the activities of scientific and practical centers at regional universities, the Regional Council for Historical and Cultural Heritage under the Akim of the region, the Scientific and Expert Commission under the regional Maslikhat.

From this point of view, it is important to create a single republic system of information, explanation and expert analysis.

Now, the quality of the interpretation and the timely dissemination of information materials are of crucial importance, both in the center and in the most remote regions.

Therefore, it is proposed to create in all region's organizations for information and education with popular scientific and analytical materials, a competent corps of lecturers-propagandists. Such organizations, called 'Madeni mura', can be integrated into regional universities and civil society institutions.

One of the socio-political priorities for the strengthening of the effectiveness of the preservation of historical and cultural heritage should be its socialization, i.e. the integration of its values into other areas of social life in the country. Obviously, this means first renewing qualitative approaches to 'reflecting' heritage in science and education.

This involves institutionalizing and introducing new historical data and cultural monuments of the Turkic civilization into the educational and methodological complex

of the subject "History of Kazakhstan" at all levels of education.

There is also a proposal for the introduction of an optional subject on the historical and cultural heritage of the Kazakh people at the level of the upper classes of secondary schools. Within the framework of higher education and science, it is proposed to introduce a republican subject Olympiad on historical and cultural heritage and to grant a scientific programme "Cultural Heritage".

In this respect, the solution of the problem will have a positive multiplicative social effect. Finally, the most important socio-political priority should be to intensify the participation of civil society institutions in the preservation of the historical and cultural heritage of the Kazakh people.

In this respect, the "spontaneity" and periodicity of civic initiatives in the erection of mausoleums, monuments, the publication of commemorative books and the implementation of onomastic projects are manifested. The involvement of civil society in the preservation of the nation's historical heritage can be deepened in the following ways:

- Encouraging the participation of representatives of civic centers in the work of all levels of councils and commissions for the protection of historical and cultural monuments.

- Initiating the development and publication of the White Book "Cultural Heritage: Status and Problems" by the civil community.

- Participate in the creation and management of the Cultural Heritage Support Fund.

- The main socio-political priorities of modernization of the system of preservation of historical and cultural heritage in Kazakhstan should become the specific benchmarks and indicators of its updated strategy.

Practical aspects of implementation of the priorities should be concentrated at the level of the following priority projects:

First, it is necessary to carry out a serious revision (optimization) of the national and regional lists of objects classified as his-

torical and architectural monuments.

They do not yet reflect the historical artefacts discovered during the years of independence and, at the same time, still include objects that can hardly be classified as historical and architectural values of our country.

Second, there is an urgent need to work out a concept for the development of the country's regional and local history museums. The current situation is described by the fact that in the museums the historical periodization is presented in different ways, many exhibits have no museum value and are connected not with the history of the region but with the history of the regional centre, there are no common criteria for identifying personalities and characters.

They reflect poorly and unsystematically the results of the national programmes "Cultural Heritage", "In the Flow of History", "Rukhani zhangiru".

Third, the republican and regional lists of sacred geographical objects were drawn up under the Rukhani Zhangiru programme. Unfortunately, these lists do not include objects of historical value to the Kazakh people, as they are located outside modern Kazakhstan.

This is why the monuments and mausoleums of Al-Farabi, Tole bi, Kurmangazy, Sultan Beibarys, Muhammad Haydar Dulati and other of our compatriots were not included in this strategically important project. In the world practice there are many examples when countries make decisions on maintenance of this type of objects at the expense of the state budget [7, 45].

Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a comprehensive and professionally verified work on compiling a list of objects of historical significance for the Kazakh people living abroad.

Taking into account the national significance of these historical monuments, it would be necessary to approve their list and maintenance procedures at the level of a decree of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Fourth, the management of measures to preserve historical and cultural heritage sites

should be accompanied by constant monitoring of their condition. It is necessary to support the point of view of a group of scientists who consider it justified and necessary to conduct a state historical and cultural expertise, to create a unified state register of cultural heritage sites and to prepare an annual report on their condition [8, p. 95].

Fifth, it is necessary to further expand the practice of inscribing objects of the historical and cultural heritage of the Kazakh people in the list of the UNESCO World Tangible and Oral Heritage Sites.

Sixth, based on ancient settlements, archaeological excavations, and complexes of historical and architectural monuments, to institutionalize the international experience of creation and functioning of national historical and cultural parks.

Seventh, to give national status and ensure the revitalization and strengthening of

the material and technical, financial and economic base of the republican state enterprise on the right of economic management "Kazrestavratsiya" of the Committee of Culture of the Ministry of Culture and Sports of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

At the same time, it is necessary to ensure the creation of its extensive network of regional branches, primarily in the regions of Turkestan, Ulytau, Atyrau, Zhambyl, Almaty, Mangystau, Abai, Eastern Kazakhstan.

International experience in ensuring the preservation of monuments and objects of historical and cultural heritage is characterized by an established financial base. Therefore, there is an objective need to create a diversified system of financing programs for the preservation of historical and cultural heritage, including at the expense of republican and regional budgets.

Данная научная статья подготовлена в рамках реализации научного проекта AP19679949 «Изучение культурного наследия в синергетических парадигмах» по грантовому финансированию фундаментальных и прикладных научных исследований на 2023-2025 годы.

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